

MICRO BIOTEC 23

CONGRESS OF MICROBIOLOGY
AND BIOTECHNOLOGY 2023

BOOK OF **ABSTRACTS**

DECEMBER
7TH - 9TH

UNIVERSIDADE DA BEIRA INTERIOR
Covilhã

P1.59 - PREDICTION OF NEUROTOXIC POTENTIAL OF AMINO ACID-DERIVED DBPS USING MOLECULAR DOCKING

Matheus M. Pereira ¹ (*), Rui C. Martins ¹

¹ University of Coimbra, CIEPQPF – Chemical Engineering Processes and Forest Products Research Center, Department of Chemical Engineering, Faculty of Sciences and Technology, Rua Sílvio Lima, Polo II, Coimbra, Portugal.

(* email: matheus@eq.uc.pt)

Keywords: Amino acid-derived DBPs; neurotoxicity; human acetylcholinesterase; molecular docking.

ABSTRACT

Disinfection By-Products (DBPs) are a class of chemical compounds formed as a result of disinfection processes in water treatment, can represent potential health and environmental risks. The most common and extensively studied DBPs, such as trihalomethanes (THMs) and haloacetic acids (HAAs), are regulated due to their known health concerns. Amino acid-derived DBPs (AA-DBPs) are chemical compounds that are formed by the oxidation and halogenation of amino acids present in natural organic matter in water sources during water disinfection processes. Due to their potential reactivity and structural complexity, amino acid-derived DBPs are of particular interest in water quality research and identification of their potential health risks remain relatively understudied. Therefore, this work aims to investigate the potential neurotoxicity of AA-DBPs. For this, the binding mechanism of several AA-DBPs on human acetylcholinesterase (AChE) were evaluated through molecular docking. The effect of halogenation degree was evaluated for mono- and di-halogenated AAs. In addition, the mechanism of AA-DBPs binding through AChE tunnels and binding affinity on enzyme active site, were calculated using Caver Web 1.0. Molecular docking results showed that most of AA-DBPs display higher binding affinity inside the access tunnels of AChE, in comparison with enzyme active site, indicating that AA-DBPs are promising AChE inhibitors, blocking AChE mechanism of breaks down the neurotransmitter acetylcholine. Thus, the identification of AA-DBPs potential neurotoxicity is here presented, highlighting the importance of further evaluation these compounds with experimental assays to obtain their level of toxicity.

Acknowledgements:

The work was developed within the scope of the project H2OforAll financed by the European Union, under the Grant Agreement GA101081953. The authors acknowledge the funding for CIEPQPF supported by the FCT through the projects UIDB/EQU/00102/2020 and UIDP/EQU/00102/2020).

Prediction of Neurotoxic Potential of Amino Acid-Derived DBPs using Molecular Docking

Matheus M. Pereira^{1,*}, Rui C. Martins¹

¹University of Coimbra, CIEPQPF – Chemical Engineering Processes and Forest Products Research Center,
Department of Chemical Engineering, Faculty of Sciences and Technology, Rua Sílvio Lima, Polo II, 3030-790 Coimbra, Portugal
*matheus@eq.uc.pt

H2OforAll

Introduction

Results

Fig 1. Tunnels in the crystal structure of human AChE: Overall structure of AChE with five tunnels: Tunnel 1 (green), Tunnel 2 (yellow), Tunnel 3 (red), Tunnel 4 (light blue) and Tunnel 5 (dark blue).

Fig 2. Profiles of the radius along the length of the AChE tunnels: Tunnel 1 (green), Tunnel 2 (yellow), Tunnel 3 (red), Tunnel 4 (light blue) and Tunnel 5 (dark blue).

Fig 3. Tunnels length (Å) and Throughput in the structure of human AChE.

Fig 4. Binding trajectory of ligands (substrate and products) going through the Tunnel 1 in the structure of human AChE.

Methods

Fig 5. Binding trajectory of ligands (AA-DBPs) going through the Tunnel 1 in the structure of human AChE.

Conclusions

Acknowledgements

The work was developed within the scope of the project H2OforAll financed by the European Union, under the Grant Agreement GA101081953. The authors acknowledge the funding for CIEPQPF supported by the FCT through the projects UIDB/EQU/00102/2020 and UIDP/EQU/00102/2020.